

LRTM – A FEASIBLE ALTERNATIVE TO VI FOR THE MANUFACTURE OF LARGE SCALE WIND TURBINE BLADES

J.R. Hutchinson, P.J. Schubel, N.A. Warrior
Polymer Composites Group, Division of Materials, Mechanics and Structures,
Faculty of Engineering, University of Nottingham,
University Park, Nottingham, NG7 2RD, UK
peter.schubel@nottingham.ac.uk

SUMMARY

This study compares LRTM with VI, a traditional blade manufacturing process. LRTM is shown in this paper to be a feasible alternative both in terms of cost and performance. Experimental observations are used to develop and verify a computational infusion simulation, allowing a comparison of the two processes for a generic 45m blade shell.

Keywords: LRTM, wind energy, blades, cost modelling, flow simulations, mould design

INTRODUCTION

Wind energy is a clean, renewable alternative to finite fossil fuels, and is a potential source for our growing energy needs. In order for it to be economically viable the production cost must be minimised as at present, around 20% of a wind turbine's total cost comes from the manufacture of its blades [1]. Therefore significant advances in blade production technology can have a major economic impact.

The LRTM Process

Light resin transfer moulding (LRTM) has been developed as a cheap alternative to current resin infusion methods such as RTM and vacuum infusion (VI). The concept uses a rigid lower mould and a semi-flexible, composite upper mould. The mould cavity, containing dry fabric, is sealed by a vacuum and resin is injected at low pressure; typically less than 2 Bar (Figure 1). This study compares LRTM technology to VI on performance and cost criteria.

Figure 1: Schematic of the LRTM process.

TECHNICAL COST MODELLING

A detailed technical cost analysis has been conducted on the shells of a generic 45m wind turbine blade. The cost model has been developed in-house and is based on an event-driven process; a sequence of events is defined for each process, each of which incurs a certain amount of raw materials and labour and may use capital equipment and tooling [2]. The methodology and calculated cost from this model have been verified by an independent aerospace company and wind energy consultancy company respectively.

No detailed consideration was given to plant layout in this work, and no allowance is made for insurance, selling costs, administration, transport, R&D etc. The results presented are dependent on a number of assumptions:

- Component program lifetime - 3 years (tooling costs are amortised over the duration of the program)
- Direct labour - £11.09/hour
- Indirect labour factor - 100%
- Interest - 7.5%
- Building cost - £72.90/m²/p.a.
- Capital equipment residual value - 5%
- Capital equipment installation - 10%
- Capital equipment auxiliary equipment cost - 15%
- Capital equipment is depreciated over 10 years

The component area and perimeter for the generic 45m blade shell were calculated as 270m² and 192m respectively. Both area and perimeter values are used throughout the model to account for material usage and floor space rental within each different manufacturing process. Basic material costs used in the model are obtained from a variety of sources. Materials and prices are based on the majority sales within the wind turbine blade manufacturing industry for that particular type of product and are assumed to be 'volume' prices where available. Wastage is set for each material individually.

Analysing the VI and LRTM cost centres with standard production parameters set for the UK manufacturing environment provides a clear indication that materials and labour make up the majority of blade manufacturing costs (Figure 2). Materials and labour costs remain independent of the production volume and account for 51% and 41% respectively for the VI process of total shell production costs (based on 1000ppa). However, a materials cost saving of 12% is seen for LRTM over that of VI due to the reduction in consumables and material waste levels. Tooling costs are shown to be considerable for LRTM at low volume levels (230ppa) due to the matched moulds and accounts for 14% of the total shell manufacture cost. However, this cost is reduced to 9% at higher volumes. The additional cost of tooling has been shown to be offset by materials savings as early as 154 ppa (Figure 3). However, due to the need to include additional tooling and labour to meet higher production volumes (seen as step changes in Figure 3), the true advantages of LRTM are not fully realised until 279 ppa. Where after, total cost savings of around 3% are seen (based on 1000ppa).

Figure 2: Three volume levels split by cost centres for the 45m shells

Figure 3: Effects of production volume on the manufacture of a VI and LRTM shell

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Tooling and Manufacture Method

The LRTM tool had a 710mm square mould surface and a 4mm thick aluminium picture-frame between the upper and lower moulds. The cavity vacuum was contained within two o-ring edge seals and a peripheral scavenger seal (Figure 1). Resin was injected centrally into a 400mm silicon line-gate which had an omega cross-section to aid resin flow. Thin strips of bleeder material were placed on the top face of the picture-frame in each corner to create four corner vents. The bottom mould was water pre-heated to 80°C and the resin was pre-heated to 25°C in the homogeniser to give it the desired viscosity of 290 mPas. The resin injection was automated by a Hyperject 3 control unit supplied by Magnum Venus Plastech. An electronic transducer measured cavity pressure, ensuring it never exceeds atmospheric, as this would result in lifting of the upper mould. The pressure transducer returns values to the control unit, operating the pneumatic injection valve accordingly.

VI injections were carried out in the heated bottom mould of the LRTM tool. The reinforcement was covered in a release film, resin diffusion layer, and vacuum bag material and sealed using mastic tape. All of these were process consumables. The vacuum ports were located in the four corners of the tool to represent the four corner vents used in the LRTM process. The resin was injected into the same line-gate so the two methods were comparable.

Materials

This study employed a two-part epoxy-based resin system specifically designed for this application by Hexcel Composites. The reinforcement, supplied by OCV, was a wind-energy grade unidirectional E-glass fabric with an aerial weight of 1265 gm⁻² and an integrated random-fibre coating to aid resin dispersion.

MECHANICAL TESTING

The modulus and UTS of the mouldings were determined using a dual column, hydraulic Instron mechanical tester. All tests were performed according to BS EN ISO 527-4, and each test was repeated five times to obtain an accurate average and prove repeatability. Precision epoxy was used to tab the specimens to ensure correct loading.

The flexural modulus and strength of the mouldings were calculated from a 3-point-bend test in compliance with BS EN ISO 178:2003, repeated five times to detect and eliminate the effect of anomalous specimens.

The only significant error in these tests came from the limits of the equipment, which were minimal. The Instron has a load accuracy of $\pm 0.5\%$, and the extensometer has an error of $\pm 0.25\text{mm}$ on the gauge length and $\pm 0.25\%$ on the reading.

Results and Discussions

Table 1 shows the LRTM laminates had marginally greater tensile and flexural strengths, while VI produced slightly stiffer mouldings. The differences in strength and modulus between the two processes are minimal and do not exceed the experimental error. At best, LRTM mouldings performed around 4% better mechanically than VI, and at worst, their performances were equal.

Table 1: Mechanical properties for LRTM and VI specimens

	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Tensile Modulus (GPa)	Flexural strength (MPa)	Flexural Modulus (GPa)
VI	733.9	38.5	790.2	31.2
LRTM	760.0	36.7	832.1	28.2

PHYSICAL PROPERTIES

By analysing the physical characteristics and structure of the mouldings, the differences between the two processing methods can be better understood and quantified.

Fibre Volume Fraction

The fibre volume fraction (V_F) gives an indication of mechanical performance as well as the level of compaction and therefore part consolidation. A burn-off test was conducted as specified by BS EN ISO 1172:1999 and was repeated eight times for each process from various locations in the laminates.

The VI process achieved a 3% increase in V_F over LRTM (Table 2), which was attributed to the fact that the LRTM process has a set cavity height, whilst the VI process allows variable compaction. The experimentally determined V_F values were lower in both cases than the theoretical predictions. This could be due to voids in the laminates which increase the total volume, reducing the fibre volume fraction; something not accounted for in the mathematical model, which assumes zero voids.

Table 2: Experimental and theoretical fibre volume fractions for each process

	Experimental Fibre Volume Fraction	Theoretical Fibre Volume Fraction
LRTM	0.46	0.50
VI	0.49	0.57

Void Content

Voids arise from air entrapment within the resin and can result in crack propagation and premature failure. Knowing and controlling the void content in a moulded component is critical in predicting how and when the part might fail. It has been shown that a 2%

increase in void content can reduce flexural strength by 20% and flexural modulus by 10% [3] - two properties which are crucial to wind turbine blades during operation.

The void analysis was conducted to BS EN ISO 7822:1999 using a statistical counting method. Eight samples were taken from various locations on each part and potted in casting resin. The surface was then polished and studied under a microscope. Image-pro software was used to measure and count void content.

The voids in the VI samples were larger and more abundant (Figure 4 top). LRTM produced lower void content, smaller voids and lower standard deviation (Table 3). This could account for the higher mechanical performance of the LRTM mouldings.

Figure 4: 5 x magnified view of worst case void for VI (top) and LRTM (bottom)

Table 3: Experimentally determined void content analysis

	% Void	Mean void (mm ²)	Standard deviation
LRTM	1.2	0.00019	0.003122
VI	2.1	0.00026	0.004735

Dimensional Accuracy

The shape and surface of a wind turbine blade's aerofoil determines how much power can be generated, so the processing accuracy is crucial. For this study, part thickness, maximum variance and standard deviation were considered. They were measured with Vernier callipers, rated with an accuracy of $\pm 0.02\text{mm}$. Each moulding was divided into a 10×10 grid and a thickness reading was taken in each square.

Table 4 shows VI produced a much thinner laminate despite having the same amount of reinforcement and injecting the same quantity of resin. LRTM gave a more controllable thickness as the picture-frame and semi-flexible upper mould restricted the cavity height variation. This also resulted in lower maximum and standard thickness variation compared to the flexible VI vacuum bag material.

Table 4: Dimensional accuracy of LRTM and VI

	Average laminate thickness (mm)	Standard Deviation (mm)	Maximum variance (mm)
LRTM	3.89	0.23	0.13
VI	3.38	0.39	0.26

PROCESS PROPERTIES

Material Wastage - Resin Loss

Both processes allow net shape moulding but experience resin loss in injection and vacuum lines. The percentage resin loss was quantified for each process using Equation 1, by determining the mass of resin injected, the finished laminate's volume and its V_F .

$$R_{wastage} = \frac{m_r - (\rho_r \times V \times (1 - V_F))}{m_r} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

m_r = mass of injected resin

ρ_r = density of resin

V = total volume of laminate

The results in Table 5 show that LRTM has a lower associated resin loss. During VI injections, resin was drawn into the vacuum lines before the part had been fully wet-out. This was less apparent in the LRTM method, as the vacuum was bled into and contained within the double o-ring seal, preventing resin from reaching the vacuum port.

Table 5: Process resin wastage

	Resin Waste (% of Resin Injected)
LRTM	4.57
VI	7.62

Fill time

LRTM offers the opportunity for higher injection pressures than VI; which depends on the strength of the applied vacuum i.e. 0.6 – 1 Bar pressure. LRTM can effectively double this as it can pressurise the tool cavity to any pressure up to atmospheric. This means a maximum injection pressure of 2 Bar can be achieved – (vacuum pressure plus atmospheric pressure), resulting in quicker injection times (Table 6).

Table 6: A comparison of experimental injection times

	Average fill time (minutes)
LRTM	15.0
VI	34.0

COMPUTATIONAL SIMULATION OF 45M BLADE MOULD-FILL

The geometry of the tool for the above experimental study was chosen for its simplicity and minimised cost. Tooling for a 45m blade exceeds the financial resources of this project, so a computational approach was needed to compare the feasibility of these processes for manufacturing large-scale wind turbine blades. PAM-RTM software was used to build a simulation that would accurately model the flow front and fill time for both VI and LRTM injections. In-house test rigs were used to determine the fabric's in-plane x and y permeability and compressibility. The resin's viscosity and density profiles and enthalpy were provided by Hexcel Composites. All other parameters such as injection pressure profiles, vacuum strength, tool and resin temperatures and V_F were set to correspond with the true values obtained through experimental mouldings. Initially the model was developed with the flat tool geometry, and the flow fronts and fill times were verified using photos and written observations from the experimental mouldings. Once the model was validated, geometry for the same generic 45m blade shell as used in the technical cost analysis was meshed using Hypermesh and run in the simulation. The type of process used for this simulation was VARI (vacuum assisted resin infusion), and differences between VI and LRTM in this model would be the injection and vacuum pressures as well as part thickness and V_F . The locations of the line-gate, injection ports and vents were then optimised to reduce fill time and resin loss. The final configuration utilised a central line-gate running the length of the blade, with injection ports at each end, and vents pulled mid-length on the leading and trailing edges. Figure 5 compares the fill times of the two processes as predicted by PAMRTM. LRTM is 2.2 times faster than VI, which agrees with the experimental findings. The percentage resin losses are 2.3% for LRTM and 3.9% for VI, the ratio and order of which is also supported by experimental results.

Figure 5: Fill times (seconds) of a generic 45m blade shell for LRTM (left) and VI (right)

CONCLUSIONS

The technical cost modelling for the VI and LRTM processes has shown that for this particular analysis of a generic 45m blade, a potential cost saving of 3% can be achieved. The analysis has assumed that labour levels remain the same for the two processes. However, in reality it would be anticipated that fewer personnel would be required to complete one LRTM moulding over that of VI and setup time would also be reduced. This would further add to the cost effectiveness of LRTM as a liquid moulding process. Unfortunately, the labour and time savings were not able to be confirmed and therefore were not included in this analysis.

Mechanically, LRTM mouldings performed up to 4% better than those produced by VI, most likely due to their lower propensity for internal void formation. LRTM also demonstrated its higher dimensional stability, reproducibility and lower material wastage. Set-up time was much quicker, and the whole process was easy to run as it required very little operator input.

The generic 45m blade shell simulation predicted a 56% reduction in fill time and a 41% reduction in resin loss; illustrating that LRTM outperforms VI when scaled up to a representative part size. Future work using a larger part could help to further verify this model and prove LRTM's performance. Overall this study has highlighted the potential of LRTM as a method for producing cheaper wind turbine blades, whilst maintaining and even improving part performance.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors of this paper would like to thank Roger Smith, Geoff Tomlinson and all the members of the AIRPOWER consortium for their help. This project was/is co-funded by the Technology Strategy Board's Collaborative Research and Development programme, following an open competition.

The Technology Strategy Board is an executive body established by the Government to drive innovation. It promotes and invests in research, development and the exploitation of science, technology and new ideas for the benefit of business - increasing sustainable economic growth in the UK and improving quality of life.

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